

HOW TO ASSESS LANGUAGE SKILLS?**Sherbekova Yulduz Zokir qizi**Teacher Department of Languages, Samarkand State Medical University,
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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to analyze various assessment and test types. Their suitability for the learner's abilities and competencies. Test modifications based on the knowledge and interests of the students.

Keywords: Assessment, tests, testing system, assessment principles, assessment profile.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important components of language learning and teaching is assessment. According to Ausubel (1968), educators should assess students appropriately and adapt their instruction to their prior knowledge. Many teachers and instructors evaluate their students in different ways based on the assessment principles (validity, dependability, practicality, authenticity, and washback), holistic and analytical scores, and various feedbacks in summative and formative settings, or in formal and informal settings. Because individual students have varied learning preferences and each group may have students of varying academic levels, for many teachers, assessing their pupils is like traveling to a new foreign country (Coombe, Folse, & Hubley, 2007). Teachers' evaluation skills can be demonstrated by their ability to test in these kinds of circumstances.

Assessment should be carried out to measure students' knowledge growth.

To accomplish this, the learner assessment profile should be mentioned. In Jambay, Samarkand, secondary school № 23 is where this project is being carried out. We chose to work with Ergasheva Sadokat, a student in this school's 11th grade. With this language learner, we did needs analysis study and repeatedly monitored her engagement in our practice to identify problems with language evaluation.

This learner is 16 years old student and has been learning English for 8 years only from school classes.

English lessons at school are conducted 3 hours a week per 45 minutes. In this turn, learners get marks for active participation and doing essential tasks and exercises. Marks are described as points: 5 points for excellent, 4 points for good, 3 points for satisfactory and 2 points for unsatisfactory participation, and completing class and home tasks. This participant always gets excellent results,

but she wants to get additional tutorial classes because she has A2 level according to CEFR standard. She needs B2 level for her entrance exam into university but their course book English 11 is intended for B1 level.

As it is known, placement tests assess students' level of language ability which should be appropriate to the course, class or grade. Such kind of tests can determine the level at which a student can learn operatively (Coombe, Folsse & Hubley, 2007). These tests are multiple choice ones, where are taken into account only language objectives with improving grammar and vocabulary. Even though the course book for 11th grade is destined for developing all macro skills, integrated grammar and vocabulary, existed assessment process don't correspond.

Established type of assessment for the 11th grade language learners assessed only profile learner's grammar and vocabulary skills which is not in appropriate level. These skills are tested based on 9 units within 6 sub-units in each which is overall 36 classes per term. This test gives 20 points in total which is 1 point for each correct answer and used as progress test for summative assessment during each term.

According to Coombe, Folsse & Hubley (2007), progress tests measure the process and development that students are doing during defined course or program goals and if students have achieved the objectives which are established in the curriculum can be included for summative assessment. But this kind of test can be used only for traditional assessment and determining learners' grammar and vocabulary skills, in other hand the reliability and validity are clear, because this test covers grammar and vocabulary parts from all units, but other macro skills like reading, writing, listening, and speaking remain almost without testing. They are assessed only in a formative way during the classes and considered as active participation in this program. Next in order, practicality of the test is determined operatively. The time is set, which is 20 minutes 1 minute for each question of the test. Scoring is organized in 5 pointed grade system which is: 5 for 17-20 points, 4 for 14-16 points, 3 for 11-13 points and 2 for 0-10 points.

Listening assessment also plays an important role for evaluating process. Listening is a receptive skill, so the assessment of listening skills can be combined by testing of reading (Arthur, 2016). For listening test I propose note-taking while listening to the track, because this activity can be very helpful for completing multiple choice questions. For listening there is also intended 20 points.

Grammar skill is suggested to be tested directly according to Arthur's (2016) ideas, so in my multimodal progress test I also decided to assess grammar separately. For this skill there is chosen multiple choice questions, which can be also considered like gap filling one. Consequently, this grammar test includes a good sample of grammatical elements. For this grammar test is intended 10 points, 0,5 point for each true answer.

Testing vocabulary can be considered as an inclusion of a grammar section. My profile participant learnt vocabulary only in traditional way with translations. Essentially, I chose to test vocabulary by matching activity, which is a helpful technique for enhancing reading skills too. For this asse Testing writing skill can be done by assessing writing skills learners' essays. In testing writing in this school teachers assess their learners in traditional way only paying attention to the grammatical organization of essays, but in this assessment I propose rubrics for assessing these essays taking into account creative, imaginative, or even intelligent knowledge. As mentioned before there are a lot of topics, which can develop learners' critical and analytical thinking abilities in English. These topics are 'Healthy lifestyle', 'Travelling', 'Historical places', 'Tourism in Uzbekistan and English speaking countries', 'Types of service in Uzbekistan and English speaking countries' and so on. ssment is destined 10 points for each true answer.

RESULTS

Having carried out this modification in all skills, we got very good results in the process of learning the English language of the tested participant of our project.

CONCLUSIONS

Assessment plays crucial role in the process of teaching and learning the English language. Teachers as gate keepers and language designers (Kaiser, 2018) should be able to assess their learners appropriately and design activities, tests according to learner's range of knowledge. This test modification project can be able to respond all these requirements. Tasks and tests in this project are proposed and organized due to profile learner's needs and her knowledge.

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